

ARCTIC PASSION

Deliverable 4.2

Disturbance map for panarctic, INTERACT sites, and WP4 local communities with permafrost disturbance trends from EO data

Version 1

15 August 2023

101003472 | Arctic PASSION

ARCTIC
PASSION

Work package

4 – Innovating user-driven Arctic
EuroGeo Pilot Services

Lead beneficiary

1 – AWI

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Status

Project Coordinator Accepted

Dissemination level

PU

This project has received funding from the
European Union's Horizon 2020 research and
innovation programme under grant
agreement No. 101003472

Executive Summary

This deliverable reports on the creation of an online tool that allows access to a panarctic permafrost disturbance map. It contributes to the 'Panarctic requirements-driven Permafrost Service', one of the pilot services created as part of Arctic PASSION in work package 4. With permafrost warming at global scale, spatially explicit information on where and to what extent landscape changes that either drive permafrost thaw or impact permafrost stability occur in the Arctic is an important factor for land management, infrastructure planning, and climate change impact mitigation. Geospatial information on such disturbances is important and may facilitate appropriate measures for dealing with land degradation caused by permafrost thaw. Disturbances such as the erosion of coasts and rivers or the subsidence of land surface through thermokarst have direct and severe influence on the livelihoods, culture, and identity of arctic residents.

In this report¹, we present the detection of permafrost disturbances using an automated processing chain for freely accessible earth observation data and the application of a Tasseled Cap transform to derive robust trend parameters. In order to make the information available to local communities and INTERACT stations, we introduce the web-based application Arctic Landscape EXplorer (ALEX). Based on experiences with a preliminary permafrost online tool in the form of a Google Earth Engine App, the new interface is tailored to the needs of users without scientific background. Through collaborations with community members the usefulness of the outcomes is ensured. Community evaluation and feedback are used to update the community-oriented maps.

Data dissemination based on internationally recognized standards and in conformance to the principles of FAIR data ensures an easy reuse of the panarctic disturbance data by scientists and other data portals. With the panarctic permafrost disturbance map an urgent need for permafrost information as part of a robust global observing system is met. For the first time, a coherent dataset on panarctic permafrost disturbance at high spatial resolution is produced and disseminated to the public. The results have the capability to substantially support planning and decision making in the Arctic.

¹ Please note that there was a delay with filling the PostDoc position tasked to improve the PS2 viewer ([chapter 2.1 and 5](#)). The position was filled with an excellent candidate in 01/2023. While our online tool ([chapter 2.1](#)) already fulfills the project requirements to build a permafrost disturbance map viewer, we will use the remaining project time to transfer the permafrost disturbance map into our new ALEX viewer ([chapter 5](#)) and add further functionalities.

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1. Introduction

Permafrost warming presents a significant threat to the Arctic region and has effects at global scale. Permafrost thaw leads to the erosion of coasts and rivers ([Lantuit et al., 2013](#); [Mann et al., 2022](#)), a subsidence of land surface through thermokarst ([Grosse et al., 2013](#)), and impacts the integrity of infrastructure ([Hjort et al., 2022](#)) among others. These permafrost-associated changes impact livelihoods, culture, and identity of indigenous and non-indigenous arctic residents ([Hovelsrud et al., 2011](#)).

To provide a concrete illustration for consequences of permafrost thaw at local level, a well-documented recent event of lake drainage can serve as a practical example (see [Jones et al., 2023](#)). On 29 June 2022 a 0.5 ha lake near Kotzebue (Alaska) started to drain into the Kotzebue Sound. The drainage of 18,500 m³ of water formed a 125-m-long thermo-erosional gully that incised 2 to 14 m in ice-rich permafrost. The gully expanded from 1 m to >10 m width and mobilized an estimated 8,500 m³ of material. Such events are widespread in northwestern Alaska which is characterized by an abundance of thermokarst lakes and ice-rich permafrost soils. [Nitze et al. \(2018\)](#) identified that within a single year, 192 lakes had completely or partially drained within their study area of 25.271 km² in northwestern Alaska.

With permafrost warming at a global scale ([Biskaborn et al., 2019](#)), it has the potential to amplify global climate change, because large amounts of soil organic carbon are stored in the northern circumpolar permafrost region ([Hugelius et al., 2014](#)). When thawing, microbes can mineralize a substantial fraction of this material which leads to a release of carbon dioxide and methane contributing to near-term climate warming in a positive feedback loop ([Schuur et al., 2015](#)).

Taking into consideration the rapid landscape change, there is a great demand for a service providing advanced warnings of recent or ongoing thaw and erosion as well as associated risks, and to support planning for mitigating the impacts of permafrost thaw. Currently, no such service is available that allows permafrost communities easy use or access. Within the Arctic PASSION project's Pilot Service 2 (PS2) this gap is being closed by providing the disturbance trends associated with abrupt permafrost degradation, aiming to enhance information distribution for better management, increased safety, and more targeted local responses.

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PS2, the panarctic requirements-driven Permafrost Service, builds upon earth observation data to provide near real time maps of surface changes of permafrost thaw. When studying very large areas, such as the arctic region, remote sensing represents the only effective way to assess landscape disturbance. At such panarctic scales most prior assessments of land surface change relied on rather coarse satellite data (250-1000m resolution), which are unsuitable for local planning and decision-making processes. However, now with the availability of high-performance processing platforms and efficient algorithms, the analysis of land surface changes and disturbance trends can be accomplished using long satellite time series such as from the Landsat-TM, ETM+ and OLI sensors (NASA/USGS) with high resolution imagery (30 m ground sampling distance, GSD) available since 1982. With ESA's Sentinel-2 mission (10 m GSD) starting in 2015, the availability of imagery has been further enhanced and dense temporal coverage has been increased.

2. Earth observation for mapping disturbance trends

For detecting disturbance trends associated with abrupt permafrost degradation, an automated processing chain for multispectral Landsat-5 TM, Landsat-7 ETM+, and Landsat-8 OLI data was developed and applied to the ~29,000 km² Arctic Lena Delta (Nitze & Grosse, 2016). In order to obtain robust trend parameters, the well-established Tasseled Cap transform was applied to all cloud-free pixels in images with less than 80% cloud-cover for the months July and August as part of the change analysis, deriving multispectral indices for changes in Greenness, Wetness, and Brightness between 1999 and 2014. Trends for each of the Tasseled Cap indices were calculated using a Theil-Sen regression (Sen, 1968; Theil, 1992) that considers the slope between every point in time and then calculates a median over the entire time period, which is defined as a master slope of the trend. The application of this approach to four extensive latitudinal transects at continental-scale demonstrated its ability to reliably detect and quantitatively assess key permafrost region disturbances such as lake drainage, thermokarst lake expansion, retrogressive thaw slumps, and fire scars across continental-scale spatial domains (Nitze et al., 2018).

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Within the ESA CCI+ Permafrost project and in collaboration with the NSF Permafrost Discovery Gateway project, we used this approach to bring the detection of permafrost disturbance trends to the next level with a 30m spatial resolution on the panarctic scale. The expanded analysis now covers the entire arctic region and was updated to the period between 2001 and 2020. Processing multiple terabytes from tens of thousands of image data also required a shift towards cloud computing. Therefore, the methodology was implemented in Google Earth Engine. The Python code was made publicly available on GitHub: https://github.com/initze/GEE_HotSpot.

Within EU Arctic Passion, the change algorithm and processing pipeline is being further refined to deliver even more robust results in areas with disrupted data sources. By the end of 2023, according to current planning, the analysis will also be updated to the period of 2004 and 2023, then also including imagery of the Landsat 9 mission (launched in September 2021) and provide a recent view of disturbance trends. The inclusion of Sentinel-2 data, available since 2015, is work in progress.

2.1. The permafrost online tool

In order to visualize the trend data at 30m resolution on a panarctic scale, and to make it available to the scientific community as well as to non-experts with a basic understanding of maps, a browser-based map application was created: <https://ingmarnitze.users.earthengine.app/view/hotspottcvisapp>. The online tool combines the Theil-Sen trends of the multispectral Tasseled Cap indices Greenness, Wetness, and Brightness in a Red-Green-Blue (RGB) image composite that allows to see different trend signatures in different colors.

In our Google Earth Engine App (**Figure 1**), the user is able to overlay the change data with high-resolution satellite imagery (Google imagery) as well as with a high-resolution digital elevation model of the Arctic (Arctic DEM; [Porter et al., 2018](#)). In the change map, flashy colors indicate a substantial change in the landscape. For example, coastal erosion (a trend of a land surface transitioning to a water surface) is depicted in dark blue colors, while coastal accretion (a trend of a water surface transitioning to a land surface) is depicted in bright orange colors. On the right-hand side of the map window the user is provided with options to directly jump to exemplary areas of clearly visible trends in

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coastal erosion, lake drainage, infrastructure expansion, and tundra fires. Here, it is also possible to generate time-series charts for the pixel-based multispectral information in the Tasseled Cap Greenness, Wetness, and Brightness indices for individual locations by clicking into the map.

The permafrost online tool is constantly evolving. The Google Earth Engine App will be further used to test various features; however, within Arctic Passion the new Arctic Landscape EXplorer (ALEX; see [chapter 5](#)) will take over as the main access point for the permafrost disturbance map both for scientific and non-scientific end-users with a scheduled release during summer 2023.

Figure 1: Screenshot of the permafrost online tool showing satellite imagery (left map view) and change data (right map view) with a slider function; blue colors at the coastline of northern Alaska indicate coastal erosion, while also some drying and lake level drop is visible with orange to yellow colors at some lakes.

3. Collaboration with local communities, INTERACT sites, partners, and beyond

When providing a Pilot Service to members of arctic communities it is a prerequisite that not only their specific information needs are met but also that aspects of co-design are considered and the information is presented in an adequate manner meeting the user requirements. Finding ways to integrate local knowledge with geospatial datasets developed by science presents an opportunity to enhance the usefulness of the permafrost disturbance products as well as increasing its usability and value to communities. Therefore, a deliberate collaboration with community members as partners is crucial for the success of this Pilot Service. The outcomes of community evaluation and feedback are regularly used to update the community-oriented maps.

We are building on community partnerships established in Arctic PASSION's Pilot Service PS1 ('Event Database of CBM Using Oral Histories, Indigenous Knowledge and Local Knowledge') and in the EU-funded Nunataryuk project as a platform for collaborative discussions and validation on the presence of thaw disturbances, and assessments of community vulnerability.

First feedback was given by community members of the Inupiaq region in Western Alaska during visits in 2022 as part of AWI's Perma-X-Scan expedition. The tool raised broad interest among the potential users such as the Northwest Arctic Borough Environmental Planning Department in Kotzebue. Given instructions on how to use the tool, the potential users were very satisfied and found it very useful. It became also clear that it is necessary to better explain the meaning of the different colors in the maps and to provide additional details on how to read the maps. It was important to show the permafrost disturbance map product in the Google Earth Engine App viewer at such a very early stage in order to ensure user-relevance and being able to better tailor the upcoming ALEX viewer to the users' needs.

For September 2023, further consultation workshops and meetings are planned in Nome (Seward Peninsula, NW Alaska) and Kotzebue (Baldwin Peninsula, NW Alaska) as part of AWI's Perma-X-Ground West Alaska expedition. In July 2023, a meeting on mapping permafrost disturbances took place with the mayor of the Town of Inuvik (NW Canada) and exchanges took place with various indigenous stakeholders in the Beaufort Delta

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region, in particular the Inuvialuit Settlement Region and the Gwich'in Lands, as part of AWI's Perma-X airborne permafrost disturbance mapping campaign. Among these stakeholders interested in better understanding the consequences of permafrost thaw were several Hunting and Trapping Committees (HTC) and the Inuvialuit Regional Corporation (IRC). In follow-up reports on the airborne campaign, we plan to also distribute digital permafrost disturbance maps. In-person interactions on the permafrost disturbance map we also had with land managers in Alaska (Selawik Fish and Wildlife Refuge of the US Fish and Wildlife Service; Environmental Planning Department of the Northwest Arctic Borough) were very positive and confirmed that the data product and a well explained, easy to use map viewer would be excellent tools to help with some of their land management obligations.

Additional discussions of the Arctic Landscape EXplorer are planned during the European Conference on Permafrost (EUCOP) in Puigcerda, Spain in June 2023 where project outcomes will be presented during a poster session. The tool will also be subject of discussion during the ESA CCI+ Permafrost progress meeting and associated ESA EO4PAC (Earth Observation for Permafrost-dominated Arctic Coasts) project meeting in Frascati, Italy in September 2023, where local Alaskan community members are invited to participate in person. Further meetings and webinars, such as part of the Strait Science Series lectures (University of Alaska Fairbanks), are in the planning phase but not yet confirmed.

The project outcomes will be of particular interest for Arctic research stations associated with the **International Network for Terrestrial Research and Monitoring in the Arctic** (INTERACT; <https://eu-interact.org/>). INTERACT is an arctic network of 74 terrestrial field bases in northern Europe, the United States, Canada, Greenland, Iceland, the Faroe Islands and Scotland as well as stations in northern alpine areas seeking to build capacity for research and monitoring all over the Arctic. (An additional 21 research stations in Russia are on pause.) We are planning to get actively into contact with INTERACT station managers and to prepare our disturbance maps and viewer in a way that they are directly accessible for each of the INTERACT research stations for their use and to help guiding permafrost and ecosystem change research with enhanced information on remotely sensed landscape disturbances in the station vicinity.

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Once the ALEX online viewer is published later in 2023 we plan to provide additional materials such as visualizations and fact sheets on changing Arctic permafrost landscapes and the ALEX viewer; we will work with Arctic Passion WP7 (Connecting the pan-AOSS with Society through Communication, Dissemination and Engagement) and WP9 (Supporting Coherent Policy and Decision-making) on the development of such materials. These fact sheets will be addressed to higher level entities such as the Arctic Council Working Groups, IASC, etc.

The **Permafrost Discovery Gateway** (PDG) project funded by the US National Science Foundation is an important partner in the further development of our disturbance data product. The PDG broadly targets development of an application for dissemination of Big Data permafrost products and will also include our disturbance map service. The use of standardized interfaces (see [chapter 4.2–4.4](#)) greatly facilitates a subsequent use of the digital information and its visualization. As direct participants in the PDG project (Grosse, Nitze) we will ensure that the permafrost landscape disturbance data product can be directly used by the PDG in their online platform.

4. Dissemination of data

In this deliverable, the core dataset disseminated to the end-users is the change analysis EO data as described in [chapter 2](#). This chapter emphasis on the dissemination of the data and its potential for technical re-use and application by other users. [Chapter 5](#) then focuses on the presentation and visualization of the data.

4.1. Processing of data

With the bulk of data processing having been conducted in the Google Earth Engine (see [chapter 2](#)), the change data reside inside Google's cloud computing environment. Access to the data through a Tile Map Service is available at no cost. However, this free service exhibits relatively slow performance. Additionally, the service URL is not persistent over time, meaning it is subject to change without prior notice. Apart from possible legal constraints, the service is therefore not suited for utilization outside the Google environment. Therefore we chose to develop our own map service for the product.

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Using different Python libraries, the image data were instead downloaded from Google Earth Engine in tiles that encompassed whole-number latitude and longitude values. Instead of including the entire dataset, a clipping operation was applied to the land-sea coastline. A buffer of 75 km was included to ensure an adequate full coverage of land areas. In a second step, an alpha channel was added in order to treat transparent pixels and the imagery was mosaiced into one large image file. As a final image product, a so-called Cloud Optimized GeoTIFF (COG) was created. This format is especially well-suited for large raster datasets and is known for its remarkable performance.

4.2. GeoServer OGC Web Map Service

We chose the GeoServer software to publish the change image data via a Web Map Service (WMS). GeoServer is a free and open source software (FOSS) and an official project of the Open Source Geospatial Foundation (OSGeo). The software is known to obey the international standards for spatial data web services elaborated by the widely acknowledged Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC). Following the service-oriented architecture of a Spatial Data Infrastructure (SDI), publishing raster data via a WMS greatly facilitates the re-use of the data. Using the appropriate service URL, a user can easily include the data into desktop geographic information systems (GIS; such as ArcMap or QGIS) as well as online map viewers based on standard map libraries (such as Leaflet or OpenLayers).

At AWI, an OGC-compliant WMS has been set up for >10 million km² already. Despite the large area covered and the file size of 130 GB, response times of the service are remarkably swift, greatly enhancing the overall user experience. The complete coverage of the arctic region will be achieved during summer 2023.

As a further improvement, the individual indices Greenness, Wetness, and Brightness, are visualized as own image layers. In order to more easily identify increase and decrease of the indices, the derivation towards the mean (no change) will be used as the base for symbolization. In GeoServer, the integration of additional layers is seamlessly achieved through the definition of styles which are interpreted directly by the server, eliminating the need for any extra data processing.

4.3. Metadata

One way to make end-users aware of existing data services is via metadata. This is especially relevant to users that do not yet know the data publisher. Via standardized metadata catalogs information about the data service is made available to search engines, portals, and other catalogs. A further task of metadata is to document the characteristics of data sets and services including a description of its limitations and use constraints.

At AWI, the [PANGAEA](#) catalogue will be used to publish metadata on both, the disturbance dataset and the associated web service. PANGAEA is member of the World Data System (WDS) of the International Science Council (ISC). Following internationally recognized standards for metadata ensures that the metadata is made accessible to a wide audience. The metadata contained within the Capabilities document of the web service will be harmonized with the contents of the catalog service metadata. The keyword 'Arctic PASSION' will be used to identify permafrost Pilot Service metadata as suggested by the guidance of the Sustaining Arctic Observing Networks ([SAON](#)). The catalog can be connected to the SAON data portal.

4.4. Interoperability and FAIR data principles

According to the FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data ([Wilkinson et al., 2016](#)), data interoperability describes the ability of data and tools, originating from multiple sources, to integrate or work together at a minimal effort. Interoperability thus greatly facilitates the reuse of data including in other applications or processing workflows.

Using geodata formats, metadata standards, and web service standards that are well established and internationally recognized as state-of-the art, we ensure a high degree of interoperability for the permafrost Pilot Service products. Test tools will be applied to check the conformity to these standards.

With this given setup, the permafrost Pilot Service effectively aligns with the FAIR data principles – Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Re-use of digital assets – as described in the Arctic PASSION data management plan (deliverable 2.1).

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5. The Arctic Landscape EXplorer (ALEX)

While the permafrost online tool in the Google Earth Engine App ([chapter 2.1](#)) offers easy access to the disturbance data for the scientific community as well as non-experts with at least some basic knowledge of maps and remote sensing data, it is not specifically tailored to non-experts who will have difficulties in interpreting the scientific information. To accomplish the goal of providing the service for use in arctic communities, the Arctic Landscape Explorer (ALEX) is being developed. It is designed to meet the information needs of local permafrost communities and stakeholders in the arctic region while at the same time an easy to use and well-explained map interface is provided.

The Arctic Landscape Explorer ([Figure 2](#)) includes a localized view on the information provided ('local view'), a mode where the map is in the centre of interest ('map view'), and a story telling component ('story maps'; see [chapter 5.1](#)). Parts of the website will be made available in multiple arctic languages.

Figure 2: Screenshot of the Arctic Landscape Explorer (ALEX), draft version, showing the start screen of a story map.

5.1. Story maps

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The seamless integration of story maps is a unique feature of the Arctic Landscape EXplorer. Story maps are an interactive approach to combine map content with multimedia elements and narrative storytelling aiming to communicate information and to engage users. In a practical manner, users are guided step-by-step to read and explore the map and thus gain a better understand of the spatially explicit data. The content of the story maps will be compiled together with members of local communities in order to build upon their local experiences and specifically take into account their views on the local situation (see [chapter 3](#)). We also plan to use results of Arctic PASSION Pilot Service 1 ‘Event Database of CBM Using Oral Histories, Indigenous Knowledge and Local Knowledge’ to further enhance and enrich the story maps.

We will initially focus on a set of seven permafrost-related topics that will be presented as story maps: thermokarst, lake change, coastal and river erosion, beaver activities, fires, hillslope erosion, and infrastructure change (see [Figure 3](#) for examples). A story map usually contains multiple slides (or pages), the user runs through one after another. While texts, pictures, diagrams, videos, oral recordings, animations, drone and aerial footage, terrain models, and many more are arranged in one part of the screen, the map window occupies the remaining screen space. Triggered by paging or other click events, the map is interactively aligned to the story content. This could be a change in location, a zooming, the change of data layers, or the display of additional data, amongst others.

5.2. Technical considerations

Prior to the implementation of the Arctic Landscape EXplorer, several key factors were taken into account. Consequently, the choice of software components was guided by factors such as a) optimizing page loading times and b) ensuring the ability to index content. Given the potential limitations of broadband access in Arctic regions, particularly in remote areas, loading times should be considerably low. To ensure the indexability of the portal’s content for search engines, solutions solely relying on JavaScript were omitted from consideration in order to allow for a better discoverability of the portal. Furthermore, a responsive design for the portal was deemed a fundamental requirement.

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Figure 3: Examples for permafrost arctic related landscape changes to be presented via story maps: a) coastal erosion, b) lake change, c) infrastructure expansion, and d) tundra fires. Left side: disturbance map view, Right side: exemplary ground or aerial view in the story map.

5.3. Technical implementation

During the evaluation of existing market solutions, it quickly became apparent that no readily available out-of-the-box solution fully met the pre-defined requirements. Consequently, the decision was made to conduct an in-house development approach utilizing existing components.

For the *map component* the open source JavaScript library Leaflet was chosen. The library is very lightweight and offers an abundance of extensions that can be easily integrated to fulfill specific desired functionalities.

Instead of using a content management system (CMS) the *page structure* and basic functionalities are deployed with custom PHP code. This approach allows for a greater flexibility in the structure of the resulting HTML code and avoids dependencies on update cycles. Furthermore, the incorporation of map functionality, story maps, and other content can be accomplished with greater flexibility. During coding, emphasis is given on maintaining a clear and well-structured code ensuring its ability to be easily adopted by any other developer.

To design the *page layout*, the decision was made to avoid using a pre-existing Cascading Style Sheets (CSS) framework. Instead, the modern CSS Grid technology was used for styling. CSS Grid, supported by mainstream browsers since 2017, is well-suited for designing modern, grid-based web interfaces and allows for dynamic and flexible layouts. Media queries are used to optimize the user experience on mobile devices. The design of the user interface was elaborated based on a graphical mock-up prior to coding.

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